

Potential Local Anaesthetics. Part VI: Synthesis of Basic N-(Substituted benzyl)-Acylamides

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α -Diethylamino N-(2-chlorobenzyl) acetamide and α -piperidino N-(2,4-dimethyl benzyl) propionamide were found earlier to have local anaesthetic and spasmolytic activity^{1,2}. To study further the structure and activity relationship, some new basic amides with variation in acyl groups have been prepared by condensing α -haloamides with secondary amines, diethyl amine, morpholine and piperidine. α -Halo amides were obtained by the condensation of 2-chloro benzyl amine (Aldrich Chemical Company, U.S.A.) and 2,4-dimethyl benzyl amine (K and K laboratories, U.S.A.) with α -halo acyl halide, which was prepared from α -bromo fatty acid by reaction with thionyl chloride. α -Bromo fatty acid was prepared as described by Vogel³.

EXPERIMENTAL

α -Bromo acyl chloride (2.0 parts) was added dropwise to an ice-cooled mixture of amine (1.4 parts), acetone (2.5 parts), sodium acetate (2.0 parts) and water (3.0 parts) with vigorous shaking. The reaction mixture was then allowed to attain room temperature and water was added to it. The precipitate thus obtained, was filtered, and washed with cold water, sodium carbonate solution (10%) and water in sequences. The substances were crystallised from petroleum ether or dilute alcohol. The compounds are described in Table I.

TABLE I

α -Bromo-N-Substituted benzyl acylamides

S.No.	R	R'	M.P. °C	Formula	% N	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	2-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	102	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ONBrCl	4.7	4.8
2.	2-Cl	C ₃ H ₇	79	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ ONBrCl	4.7	4.6
3.	2-Cl	C ₄ H ₉	63-64	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ ONBrCl	4.4	4.4
4.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂ H ₅	130	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ ONBr	4.8	4.9
5.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₃ H ₇	102	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ ONBr	4.6	4.7
6.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₄ H ₉	87-88	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ ONBr	4.6	4.5

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α -Bromo N-benzyl acyl amides were then condensed with secondary amine by methods as described by Dalal and Trivedi¹. Characteristics of the compounds thus obtained are described in Table II.

TABLE II.

B = Diethylamino

Sr. No.	R	R'	M.P. °C	Formula	% N	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	2-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	137-138a	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ ON ₂ Cl.C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	13.6	13.7
2.	2-Cl	C ₃ H ₇	124a	C ₁₆ H ₂₅ ON ₂ Cl.C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	13.2	13.3
3.	2-Cl	C ₄ H ₉	127-128a	C ₁₇ H ₂₇ ON ₂ Cl.C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	13.2	13.0
4.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂ H ₅	169b	C ₁₇ H ₂₈ ON ₂ .HCl	9.0	9.0
5.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₃ H ₇	172a	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ ON ₂ .C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	13.6	13.5
6.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₄ H ₉	138-140a	C ₁₉ H ₃₂ ON ₂ .C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	13.0	13.1

B = Morpholino

7.	2-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	79	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	9.5	9.5
8.	2-Cl	C ₃ H ₇	83	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	8.9	9.0
9.	2-Cl	C ₄ H ₉	167a	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	12.8	12.7
10.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂ H ₅	117	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂	9.7	9.7
11.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₃ H ₇	105	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂	9.0	9.2
12.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₄ H ₉	92	C ₁₉ H ₃₀ O ₂ N ₂	8.9	8.8

B = Piperidino

13.	2-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	156b	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ ON ₂ .Cl.HCl	8.3	8.5
14.	2-Cl	C ₃ H ₇	176a	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ ON ₂ Cl.C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	13.2	13.0
15.	2-Cl	C ₄ H ₉	64-65	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ ON ₂ Cl	8.6	8.7
16.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂ H ₅	169-170b	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ ON ₂ .HCl	8.6	8.6
17.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₃ H ₇	66	C ₁₉ H ₃₀ ON ₂	9.2	9.3
18.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₄ H ₉	160-161a	C ₂₀ H ₃₂ ON ₂ .C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	12.9	12.8

a = picrate, b = hydrochloride.

Pharmacological Results : Compounds No. 4, 13, 14, 16 (Table II) when administered as 2% solution in 1.2% saline were found to have significant local anaesthetic activity compared to procaine hydrochloride as tested by the modified method of Kuna and Seeler^{4,5}.

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